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**Of Mob and Madness: Mob Lynching in Saharu Nusaiba Kannanari's
*Chronicle of an Hour and a Half***

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Abstract:

The paper attempts to read the mob lynching that is portrayed in Saharu Nusaiba Kannanari's novel, *Chronicle of an Hour and a Half*, as a collective crime driven by sexual jealousy, applying the arguments postulated by Gustave Le Bon on crowd psychology and René Girard's idea of the scapegoat. The intersection of these two theoretical lenses gives a deep sense of understanding of the layered nature of mob lynching and how it is materialised in a normative modern society. By performing a close textual analysis of the novel, the paper attempts to look deeply into the formation of crowds, its unity, and the unseen factors that lead to the irreversible act of lynching.

Keywords: Mob Lynching, Sexual Jealousy, Mob Violence, Scapegoat.

Introduction

Sharu Nusaiba Kannanari's debut novel, *Chronicle of an Hour and a Half*, presents the turn of events over the period of one and a half hours on a rainy Friday afternoon in a small village

named Vaiga, in Areekode, Kerala. At the heart of the narrative is the adulterous relationship between Burhan, a 25-year-old man, and Reyhana, a woman in her forties, who is married and is mother to two daughters who are in their twenties. The smooth flow of their lives changes on a random Friday afternoon as the news of the clandestine affair between the two leaks through WhatsApp. The circulation of the news by vested parties ultimately leads to Burhan getting lynched by a large group of men in a mad frenzy.

The paper offers a close textual analysis of the novel through the intersection of Gustave Le Bon's *The Crowd: A Study of the Popular Mind* and René Girard's *Violence and the Sacred*. It thereby attempts to uncover the interdisciplinary interpretative possibilities of the novel and understand the layered nature of mob lynching portrayed in it. This study also challenges or counters any unidirectional or reductive reading of mob behaviour. The paper argues that the reason that led to the protagonist's lynching is not the moral outrage of the society trying to punish the adulterous relationship. Instead, it was the frustrated energy and rivalry that stemmed from sexual jealousy that culminated in the violent acts. It further goes on to argue that the crowd functioned as an extension of the psyche of the impotent man, Shahid, who instigated the lynching.

Reading the text through the lens of two different yet complementary theories illuminates its representation of mob violence. It contributes significantly to generic discussions about mob lynching, which is an area that requires academic and critical attention in contemporary society.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for the paper is drawn from two texts of utmost importance when looking at the psychology of crowd behaviour: *The Crowd: A Study of the Popular Mind* by Gustave Le Bon and *Violence and the Sacred* by René Girard. Le Bon's work laid the foundation

for studying crowd psychology and cannot be overlooked in any research on mob violence. Le Bon argues that the crowd feels and acts intensely, and there is absolutely no role for rationality in their deeds, as it is entirely emotional and unconscious. He posits, "...a crowd perpetually hovering on the borderland of unconsciousness, readily yielding to all suggestions, having all the violence of feeling peculiar to beings who cannot appeal to the influence of reason, deprived of all critical faculty, cannot be otherwise than excessively credulous" (Le Bon 17). Le Bon elaborates on the "certainty of impunity" (22) that a crowd possesses. He also says that this certainty grows stronger as the members of the crowd increase. Le Bon also puts forth the idea that, in a crowd, the members, including the foolish and the envious, are deprived of their sense of insignificance and powerlessness and are "possessed by a sense of brutal and temporary but immense strength" (22). In the novel, a heterogeneous group of hundreds of men points unequivocally to one outcome, the murder of Burhan. This exemplifies that despite their individualities, lived experiences, and various social standings, all of them, the entire crowd, work towards only one aim. And this is precisely how individual behaviour changes in a crowd.

The paper intends to look at Burhan, the guy being lynched by the hostile crowd, as a perfect example of 'human scapegoat', an idea introduced by René Girard in *Violence and the Sacred*. Girard says: "any community that has fallen prey to violence or has been stricken by some overwhelming catastrophe hurls itself blindly into the search for a scapegoat. Its members instinctively seek an immediate and violent cure for the onslaught of unbearable violence and strive desperately to convince themselves that all their ills are the fault of a lone individual who can be easily disposed of" (79). It is worth noting that Girard mentions how collective forms of violence, like lynching, justify themselves by making accusations like incest, infanticide, and

parricide. In *Chronicle of an Hour and a Half*, it is the adulterous relationship between a married woman and a young man who is around twenty years younger than her.

Subsequently, he says that scapegoating is a mechanism that communities use during times of chaos to restore the lost social order. So, in such contexts, a person is chosen and is eliminated from society. This is considered an act of symbolically cleansing society. In the novel, Burhan's act of engaging in an adulterous relationship with a married woman was perceived as corrupt behaviour, and hence he was chosen as the 'human scapegoat'.

Girard's scapegoating framework in *Violence and the Sacred* propounds that desire is mimetic, and in a society where the desires are kept secret or cannot be fulfilled, tension is created. This tension ultimately leads to the killing of the scapegoat, who is considered a rival by the crowd. Girard talks about how the scapegoat mechanism has also found its way to modern societies, which can be observed in the ways of communal and various other forms of violence stemming from mimetic rivalry.

Jealousy and Mimetic Rivalry

As Michael Shepherd says, "Jealousy is a notoriously dangerous passion and constitutes a well-recognised motive for crimes of violence, particularly of a genocidal nature". And it is indeed jealousy that leads to the lynching that is carried out by the mob in the novel; jealousy of the impotent male against the potent male, and jealousy of a crowd packed with men who are offended when they learn that somebody is actually engaging in something they cannot accomplish themselves, but is internally longing for. Burhan's lynching in the novel can be read as a collective crime born out of extreme sexual jealousy of Shahid, whose wife abandons him for a potent man, which was in turn transferred to the crowd through WhatsApp messages and instigates the

lynching. The crowd acts as a mirror of Shahid's psyche, performing the lynching and thereby attempting to restore the symbolic order of the society, where the masculine authority is not questioned.

Shahid, the person who instigates the mob through WhatsApp messages and calls, is an impotent man whose wife ran away with a mullah, taking their baby, which was later revealed to be not Shahid's own. While living with the pain of not being enough, Shahid must have waited for an opportunity to exact revenge upon his wife. So when Chinnan, who witnessed Burhan going to Reyhana's home, calls up Shahid to inform him about what he saw, Shahid knew precisely what he should do. Shahid circulates the hot news among all the prevalent WhatsApp groups in the village hoping that the crowd will teach Burhan a lesson. Burhan's lynching was a symbolic revenge for Shahid, who also later admits that he does not regret instigating the mob. The crowd that forms around the clash in the Bazaar between Burhan's four brothers and Reyhana's Brother-in-law, Saud, and his four sons, gets excited by witnessing all the violence.

Meanwhile, the WhatsApp group chats, which started with the messages from Shahid, turned into a violent tirade with people calling for bloodshed and murder. Undoubtedly, the root of all this is Shahid, and his internalized lack of manliness. It can be observed that the reason that ultimately leads to the lynching of Burhan is sexual jealousy.

The crowd that is formed in the Bazaar behaves as if every man's honour is bestowed upon Reyhana and she has ruined it by starting a sexual relationship outside marriage, that too with a young man who is very much younger than her. The anger also signifies that the crowd has taken the loss of dignity of one man, i.e, Reyhana's husband Sadique, personally. "The anger was general. Sadique's wife was somehow everyone's wife or mother or sister or whatever, even for people who had never known Burhan or heard Reyhana's name at all" (Kannanari 100). When the

crowd vandalizes Reyhana's home and enters her bedroom where she lies with her lover Burhan, the crowd physically abuses Burhan and sexually violates Reyhana's body:

They were banging on the door downstairs. I could hear men talking and shouting, screaming for Burhan and his bitch... I could hear the main door break open. I could hear the rush of men downstairs, flinging the doors to the rooms violently open and then running up the stairs, and before I could let out a scream, the door we sat looking at burst open and slammed against the wall. The men stormed in, swearing and hollering and chanting kill kill kill... a metal rod struck Burhan's skull, and before I could hear his meek, stunned cry for pain, hot burning blood from his mouth splattered on to my face and the phone in his hand flew in the air and smashed against the wall. And then I could see nothing for an instant. They swooped down upon him like hyenas and somebody pulled me by my hair and another grabbed my breast and yet another my arm and my butt until I could no longer tell where all my body was being violated and by how many hands (150).

This incident in itself is the most significant testimony to the fact that it was not Shahid's sexual jealousy alone that took things to a bloody turn. However, the whole group of men were sexually jealous of Burhan, and considered him a rival since the news was leaked through WhatsApp. In their inner psyche, they all desired what Burhan had got, Reyhana. Since desires of this kind should not be said out loud, the repressed desire in them took the form of violence, which they inflicted upon Burhan's body, whom I argue is the scapegoat in the narrative. Girard postulates how rituals of sacrifice are conducted to contain the violence generated by 'mimetic rivalry', the rivalry which arises from 'mimetic desire', which is desiring the same object as someone else.

However, even Shahid, the prime enabler of the violence, is reluctant to admit that it is his sexual jealousy or frustration that he let out by forming the mob. When his father accuses him of

instigating a mob, “You hate Burhan because he is more than you and he reminds you of the disgrace of your wife’s desertion of you and you are still suffering. That’s why you did this” (161), he flares up. His father blames him for the role he played in perpetuating the hate crime, to which he retorts that he was concerned with the immorality involved and did all that for his brethren toiling in the Persian Gulf when their wives are engaging in such adulterous relationships: “We live and work so far away from home to feed those at home. And it's not something unique to Sadique and I. There are many many wives like his and mine and yes, I do intend to put an end to this, here in this village at least, and yes it feels personal to do this to Burhan. It feels exciting. It fucking does.” (163). Though Shahid never admits it, as one of the youngsters from the village, Deepu, says, it is undeniable that the violent event that took place was the "rage of an impotent man" (171).

The Crowd and the Scapegoat

I intend to employ Gustave Le Bon’s analysis of the crowd from *The Crowd: A Study of Popular the Mind* to analyze the act of lynching performed in the novel and thereby to understand the behaviour of the crowd, and its psychology. The arguments of Le Bon are of key significance, especially in the contemporary social scenario, when people have started employing social media as a tool to form violent masses and unleash aggression, both online and offline. The major argument that Le Bon makes in his foundational text is that the crowd functions as an amplifier of passion. Whatever emotion it is, be it anger, violence, or frustration, all the members of the crowd pick up on the emotion really soon, and it in turn becomes the core emotion of the entire crowd. Thus, in the novel, the calls for killing, which are initially started by individuals, are later taken up by the entire group. A pressing urge to see Burhan's blood infects the crowd. The anger and

aggression spread like wildfire among every member of the crowd, and they all, as Le Bon says in his text, suddenly lose their ability to think individually and start thinking and acting like one entity:

The most striking peculiarity presented by a psychological group is the following. Whoever be the individuals that compose it, however like or unlike be their mode of life, their occupations, their character, or their intelligence, the fact that they have been transformed into a group puts them in possession of a sort of collective mind which makes them feel, think, and act in a manner quite different from that in which each individual of them would feel, think, and act were he in a state of isolation. Certain ideas and feelings do not come into being, or do not transform themselves into acts, except in the case of individuals forming a group. The psychological group is a provisional being formed of heterogeneous elements, which for a moment are combined, exactly as the cells which constitute a living body form by their reunion a new being which displays characteristics very different from those possessed by each of the cells singly (Le Bon 17).

Le Bon firmly states that, if each individual in the group were standing alone, they would not even have dared to consider committing such a heinous crime. As they were standing as a group, they got the courage to commit such an unspeakable crime: "Moreover, by the mere fact that he forms part of an organised group, a man descends several rungs in the ladder of civilisation. Isolated, he may be a cultivated individual; in a crowd, he is a barbarian — that is, a creature acting by instinct. He possesses the spontaneity, the violence, the ferocity, and also the enthusiasm and heroism of primitive beings" (20). Each individual might have felt invisible when standing as part of the crowd, as the crowd does not possess a face. The crowd develops its own psyche and unleashes deeds that even barbarians might hesitate to attempt. When an individual becomes a part

of the crowd, he forgets about the rules and laws of the state and fearlessly engages in horrendous acts. In the novel, they were all working towards one aim: killing Burhan and putting an end to what was going on between him and Reyhana.

Each chapter of the novel is in the form of first-person accounts by various characters who make brief appearances to recount their share of the story. The account by Fanny, the son of a teacher from the village, is scary and makes one understand the depths to which even a teenager stoops when he becomes a part of the excited mass. Fanny records the lynching on his mobile phone without even a tinge of sympathy for Burhan, the person who was being butchered, and derives a kind of pleasure from being a part of the crowd. He seriously contemplates raping Reyhana after the angry mob goes outside the house, taking Burhan's violated body. This indicates the power of crowds and how it strips people of socially acceptable behavior regardless of their age group. Even small boys were not afraid of what was happening in front of their naked eyes. They were seen enjoying the spectacle and refused when their parents tried to escort them home: "Parents were escorting children away and bossy big brothers were excited striplings, stick in hands, censoring, and the unwilling boys were revolting, screaming, jumping back, like mad dogs on leashes" (172).

In *Violence and the Sacred*, Girard talks about how the scapegoat mechanism, through various acts of collective violence, manifests in modern society as well. In the novel, the character of Burhan is the scapegoat, and by destroying Burhan's body, the crowd relieves the tension that is built up due to their unfulfilled desires. Burhan becomes the scapegoat for the society's accumulated frustration, simply because, at twenty-five, he possessed something they all coveted but could never acknowledge. Freud in *Civilization and Its Discontents* talks about how living with other people in society makes individuals repress their desires for the sake of co-existence. The

character, Gopu's comment, "All the bastards ranting like crazy on WhatsApp wish it were them and not Burhan sucking on her...I think all these men including you, my righteous asshole, wanted to spank her bum and suck on her titties, they didn't like it when only one of them succeeded" (126), exposes the crowd's mentality, and also the true motive behind the crime. It was not their moral concerns or sympathy for Reyhana's expatriate husband or even her daughters that made them rush into Reyhana's home and unleash the animals in them. It was the common desire and the mimetic rivalry they held towards Burhan that was the reason behind the gruesome incident. As Girard observed, the collective desire for one thing turned into rivalry, and it eventually ended up making Burhan the scapegoat.

Conclusion

The paper critically examined mob lynching as portrayed in the novel *Chronicle of an Hour and a Half* by Saharu Nusaiba Kannanari, with an impetus on the ideas of crowd behavior and sexual jealousy. Through a close textual analysis of the novel, the paper demonstrated that the lynching performed in the novel is nothing but an outpouring of the sexual jealousy that has been accumulated in a man's psyche over time, which was later seen to be infecting the entire crowd. The shame of not being enough of a man, due to his impotence, is deeply ingrained in Shahid's psyche, and this is what encourages him to instill the people of the village with anger and rage towards Burhan, who reminds Shahid of his lack. Furthermore, the paper also employs Le Bon's ideas to examine in detail the reasons for mob violence and how mob behaviour strips its members of their individuality. The reading dismantles the idea or notion that it was the moral concerns of the crowd that led to the murderous event.

Through these observations, the paper calls for attention to the portrayal of mob lynching in literature and its numerous undercurrents. Rooted in an interdisciplinary perspective, it encourages academicians from various disciplines to engage more closely with the concept of mob lynching and how literature and visual media portray it, especially in the regional context, as such representations are limited. The novel stands out as a distinctive addition to Indian English Literature because it explores a theme that is seldom chosen for a storyline, even though it represents one of the crucial challenges confronting our civilized society. By dealing with an issue that is unsettling and of great seriousness, Saharu's novel is one that may not be overlooked. Mob lynching is no longer a standalone phenomenon in our society, yet not many writers have taken up the subject. Considering his depiction of mob lynching with all its intricacies, Saharu's novel is a text of utmost contemporary relevance.

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